

2 **Determination of Am-241 conversion coefficients** 3 **and proposition for filtered S-Am beams**

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22 **ABSTRACT:** Am-241 sources are used for radiation protection meter calibrations, the radiation
23 quality being denoted as S-Am. Because the differences in source encapsulation affect the low
24 energy photon contribution to the fluence spectrum, currently, conversion coefficients from air
25 kerma to dose equivalent (CCs) need to be determined for each individual source by spectrometric
26 measurements. In this work, we propose using additional filtration in the S-Am beams, making
27 the CCs independent of the source encapsulation and allowing the use of generic CCs without the
28 necessity to use spectrometry. The effect of different filter materials on the CCs was studied by
29 Monte Carlo simulations, and validated by spectrometric measurements. The recommended added
30 filtration is 0.25 mm of copper and 0.4 mm of aluminum, and generic CCs that can be used with
31 this filtration are given. In addition to the CCs being insensitive to source encapsulation thickness,
32 issues with energy response of detectors related to differing X-ray contribution between different
33 S-Am beams are solved by the added filtration. Therefore the authors recommend using the added
34 filtration in all S-Am calibration beams.

35 **KEYWORDS:** Dosimetry concepts and apparatus; Models and simulations; Radiation calculations;
36 Spectrometers

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50 1 Introduction

51 Am-241 radionuclide sources are used for radiation protection instrument calibrations due to the
52 main gamma peak energy at 59.5 keV. The sources allow calibration at lower photon energy than
53 with the commonly used Cs-137 (main gamma peak at 662 keV) or Co-60 sources (1172 keV and
54 1332 keV). The emission spectrum from the decay of Am-241 contains also a non negligible number
55 of gamma emissions at 26.3 keV and 33.2 keV as well as X-ray emissions from 12 keV to 22 keV. In
56 an S-Am irradiation set-up, the spectrum contains in addition characteristic X-rays produced in the
57 source capsule and source collimators (the collimator designated to shape the beam). The photons
58 below the 59.5 keV energy can have a non-negligible contribution to the measured air kerma and
59 dose equivalent.

60 Obsolete version of ISO 4037-3:1999 standard provided recommended values for conversion
61 coefficients from air kerma to dose equivalent (denoted in the rest of the document as CC) for S-Am
62 beams if the source capsule window is at least 0.32 g/cm^2 [1]. Due to the various available designs
63 of Am-241 sources, it was difficult to ensure that the encapsulation requirement was met. Also,
64 there was very little data available on S-Am beam spectra, and the revised ISO 4037-3:2019 [2]
65 provided the CC values as an estimate only and stated that it is necessary to determine the CC values
66 individually for each S-Am beam. However, it is difficult to fulfill this requirement for a reference
67 laboratory without established method for spectrometry of X-ray beams.

68 Determination of CCs for S-Am beams has been studied in previous publications [3, 4]. In
69 calculations of CCs from fluence spectra, a lower energy limit for the calculation needs to be applied
70 to prevent detector effects from distorting the calculated result. Even though the contribution to

71 fluence would be small, due to high value of mass transfer attenuation coefficients at low energies,
 72 the contribution to air-kerma, and thus to CCs may not be negligible (see equation (2.3)). In [3],
 73 a lower limit for calculations was set to 16 keV, an energy slightly below $L\beta$ X-rays of Np-237
 74 (daughter nucleus in decay of Am-241). In [4] the lower limit was 35 keV, and the limit was
 75 justified by a thick stainless steel protection case. However, within this study, it became evident that
 76 the spectrum from the S-Am sources contains characteristic X-rays from the steel encapsulation of
 77 the source, affecting the CCs significantly. The energy of these X-rays ranges from about 6 keV
 78 onward, and the spectrometry method should work down to these energies for reliable determination
 79 of the CCs. Also, the characteristic X-rays from the source collimators may have a non-negligible
 80 impact on the spectrum at low energies. For the STUK spectrometer, fluence values below 10 keV
 81 became erroneous [3].

82 A proposed alternative for using spectrometry is to include an additional layer of materials (a
 83 filter) in front of the Am-241 source that removes the low energy photons from the spectrum. For
 84 the filtered beams, tabulated CC values could be used without necessity to do spectrometry. A
 85 Monte Carlo (MC) study was performed to find optimal filtration material and its thickness when
 86 the CC value is practically insensitive to an additional increase of the filter thickness. In addition to
 87 allowing the use of generic CCs without spectrometry, the filtered beam also becomes arguably more
 88 suitable for calibration purposes due to harmonization of the S-Am spectra between laboratories,
 89 reduction of uncertainties related to detector energy response, and more monoenergetic nature of
 90 the beam. Recommendation on the filter thickness, filter geometry, and generic CCs that can be
 91 used with this filtration are given.

92 In this study, thickness filters is expressed in mm or g/cm^2 . The former is used mainly for
 93 stating the recommended thickness of the filters, whereas the latter is used mainly for consistency
 94 with the ISO 4037 data and to compare the results obtained with different materials.

95 2 Methods

96 2.1 Calculation of CCs

97 Air kerma can be calculated from a fluence spectrum with equation

$$K_a = \sum_{i=1}^n K_{a,i} = \sum_{i=1}^n \phi_i E_i \left(\frac{\mu_{\text{tr}}}{\rho} \right)_{E_i}, \quad (2.1)$$

98 where ϕ_i is the fluence in bin i of the spectrum, E_i is the center energy of bin i , and $(\mu_{\text{tr}}/\rho)_{E_i}$ is the
 99 mass energy transfer coefficient at energy E_i . $K_{a,i}$ is the air kerma caused by photons in bin i , and
 100 is called air kerma spectrum. A dose equivalent is calculated from the air kerma spectrum with

$$H = \sum_{i=1}^n K_{a,i} h_{E_i} = \sum_{i=1}^n \phi_i E_i \left(\frac{\mu_{\text{tr}}}{\rho} \right)_{E_i} h_{E_i}, \quad (2.2)$$

101 where h_{E_i} is the monoenergetic CC at energy E_i . Monoenergetic CCs are provided in ISO 4037-
 102 3:2019 [2]. More recent values, calculated in a single consistent way and in much shorter energy
 103 steps, reducing the uncertainties of interpolated coefficients, are given in [5]. A CC for the spectrum

104 is calculated with

$$h_K = \frac{H}{K_a} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \phi_i E_i \left(\frac{\mu_{tr}}{\rho} \right)_{E_i} h_{E_i}}{\sum_{i=1}^n \phi_i E_i \left(\frac{\mu_{tr}}{\rho} \right)_{E_i}}. \quad (2.3)$$

105 At the energies of the Am-241 decay, mass energy absorption coefficients $(\mu_{en}/\rho)_E$ can be used
106 instead of $(\mu_{tr}/\rho)_E$ with negligible added uncertainty [6]. This is due to the low radiative yield at
107 the energies of interest. The unrenormalized NIST XCOM $(\mu_{en}/\rho)_E$ values from ICRU 90 [7] were
108 used, and the data were interpolated with a 4-point Lagrange polynomial on logarithmic-logarithmic
109 scale. The h_E values were interpolated with 4-point Lagrange polynomial on linear-linear scale.

110 2.2 Monte Carlo simulations of additional filter thickness

111 A suitable filter material should have low proton number to minimize the energy of emitted char-
112 acteristic photons, should be easy to obtain and handle, and should have very low impurity con-
113 tent and well-known elemental composition, thickness and density. Therefore, aluminum (Al,
114 $\rho = 2.7 \text{ g/cm}^3$) and copper (Cu, $\rho = 8.96 \text{ g/cm}^3$) were selected for testing. Stainless steel was
115 also included in the simulations for comparison purposes, and to test the effect of source capsule
116 thickness. However, the composition and density of steel are often not exactly known, and therefore
117 it was not considered a suitable filter material for the recommended additional filtration.

118 Monte Carlo (MC) simulations were performed with a general-purpose radiation transport
119 code MCNP® version 6.2 [8] with electron-photon relaxation library EPRDATA14 [9]. Electron
120 transport was turned off, but characteristic and bremsstrahlung photons created by electrons were
121 included using a thick-target bremsstrahlung model (parameter *ides*=0). Photon energy cut was set
122 to 3 keV. The modeled geometry included the source, filtration, and air.

123 Energy distribution of photons originated in the source volume consisted of all X-ray and
124 gamma emissions of Am-241 given in [10]. The source was either a point source or a volume
125 source (4 mm radius, 2 mm thick) in ceramics (3 Al₂O₃ + 2 SiO₂, $\rho = 2.7 \text{ g/cm}^3$, abbreviated as
126 CER) enclosed in stainless steel (316LN type, $\rho = 8.0 \text{ g/cm}^3$, thickness 0.05 g/cm², abbreviated as
127 ss). Encapsulation thickness was chosen about 3x lower than that in typical real sources in order
128 to avoid underestimation of the recommended thickness of additional filters. The examined filter
129 combinations were Al only, Cu only, stainless steel (316LN) only, Cu + Al, and stainless steel + Al.
130 With the combinations of Cu + Al and stainless steel + Al, the aluminum thickness was 0.4 mm. The
131 thickness was chosen to decrease the flux of the characteristic photons from Cu (energy 8-9 keV) by
132 roughly a factor 10³. The filters were positioned at a distance of 1 cm from the source and covered
133 the whole cross section of the beam collimated to a cone with 80° opening angle. The simulation
134 geometry is visualized in Figure 1.

135 The energy distribution of photon fluence was scored at various distances from the source front
136 surface using a point detector F5-type tally. This tally is a deterministic estimate of the flux at a
137 point calculated at every collision of a particle from the probability of the particle scatter towards
138 the detector and the probability of a collision-less free flight from its current position to the detector
139 position. The CCs were determined from the fluence spectra with equation (2.3).

140 Validity of the MC simulations was tested by comparison with estimated CC values in ISO
141 4037-3:2019. The simulated CC values were obtained in air at a distance of 200 cm from a source
142 with a ceramic active volume and 0.32 g/cm² steel encapsulation.

Figure 1. Schematics of the modelled geometry.

Figure 2. Am-241 sources of various construction measured at CMI. Left to right: EG type, EM type, XRF type and ANG300. Images are not to scale.

143 2.3 Spectrometry of Am-241 sources

144 S-Am spectrometric measurements to validate the results from MC simulations were performed at
 145 two locations with independent methods, at CMI and at ENEA. At CMI, fluence spectra of Am-241
 146 sources of four different constructions (Figure 2) were measured. Only one of them was dedicated
 147 for dosimeter tests, while the others were included in this study for comparison purposes only. The
 148 specifications of the sources are presented in Table 1. An industrial source, ANG300, was produced
 149 in 1984, and its construction, and especially encapsulation, is assumed to be very similar to an
 150 AMC65 source sold by Ecker&Ziegler (Germany) recently [11]. The second source is an industrial
 151 annular source designed for X-ray fluorescence analysis (referred to as the XRF source). The EG-
 152 type source is a point-like sealed source for γ -ray spectrometer calibrations. In the EM-type source
 153 designed for calibration of instruments measuring α and β emitting radionuclides, the activity is
 154 plotted as dots onto the surface and then covered with a layer of sprayed varnish.

155 At CMI, spectrometry was performed with a compact commercial detector X-123CdTe (AMPTEK
 156 Inc., USA) [13] with a 3 mm \times 3 mm \times 1 mm (width, height, thickness) cadmium telluride (CdTe)
 157 sensor and 100 μ m thick beryllium window allowing to measure photons with an energy $>$ 4 keV.
 158 The spectrometry measurement setup is described in [14, 15].

159 The detector was shielded from the side and the front by 2 mm thick tungsten cover. The
 160 aperture in its front face had a diameter of 2 mm, except for the measurement of the EM source,

Table 1. Specification of various Am-241 sources measured at CMI.

Type	Manufacturer	Nominal activity	Active volume diameter (mm)	Window material and thickness
ANG300	Institute for the Research Production and Use of Radioisotopes (UVVVR), Czechoslovakia	11 GBq	11	stainless steel, 0.2–0.25 mm (0.16–0.2 g/cm ²)
XRF	Amersham Corporation and AEA Technology, QSA Global, Inc	1 GBq	annulus, 40 mm inner diameter, 5 mm thickness	beryllium, unknown thickness
EG	CMI [12]	< 1 MBq	3	1.5 mm polystyrene
EM	CMI [12]	a few kBq	48.5 (nominal)	sprayed varnish and aluminized, <300 μg/cm ² total surface density

Figure 3. Detector spectra of Am-241 sources of different construction measured at CMI. See Section 2.3 and Figure 2 for source acronyms used in the legend.

161 which was performed without the front shielding to increase the detector count rate. Pulse-height
 162 spectra of impulses in the detector ("*detector spectra*"; Figure 3) were acquired at a distance
 163 between the source surface and the front face of the detector collimator (the collimator at the
 164 detector designated for detector shielding) of 1.8 cm (EM source), 10 cm (EG source), and 30 cm
 165 (ANG300 and XRF sources). The distance was measured using a calibrated metal gauge.

166 MC simulations for the additional filter thicknesses (section 2.2) were verified by measurements.

167 The purpose of these measurements was not to calculate the CCs, but rather to confirm that the low
168 energy photon contribution to the fluence spectrum is minimized by the added filtration. The EG
169 type source was used to confirm the thickness of the main filter (1st filter). This source was selected
170 because, unlike with the ANG300 source, a significant portion of the low energy photons penetrate
171 its 1.5 mm thick polystyrene encapsulation (for 20 keV photons, this thickness corresponds to a Cu
172 thickness of 2.2 μm only) allowing to test the main filter thickness, although the count rate at the
173 detector positioned 10 cm from the source reached about 20 s^{-1} only. The detector was covered
174 with a shielding against photons scattered from surrounding objects.

175 The thickness of the second filter (Al) was verified by another set of measurements performed
176 with the ANG300 source. The detector was positioned 45 cm from the source reaching a count
177 rate of 5000 – 10000 s^{-1} . In these measurements, no collimator was attached to the detector to
178 ensure that the measured spectrum remained unaffected by characteristic photons generated in the
179 collimator, which could interfere with the characteristic peaks of Cu filter. In all such measurements,
180 the sources were not collimated and the spectra were acquired for a range of filter thicknesses. The
181 standard uncertainty of the thickness of the filters was 6% for 100 μm thick filter, 4% for 200 μm
182 and 250 μm thick filters, and 3% for 300-500 μm thick filters.

183 The results with the additional filtration were verified by measurements at ENEA. An Amer-
184 sham 3158LV source with X.93 capsule and approximately 37 GBq activity was measured with
185 additional filtration of 0.25 mm of Cu and 0.4 mm of Al. The source window thickness was given
186 as 0.2 mm – 0.25 mm of steel. The spectrometer was another unit of AMPTEK X-123CdTe. A
187 non-customised, standard shielding and detector collimator set provided by the manufacturer was
188 used with a 400 μm diameter collimator aperture. The distance between the source and the filter
189 set was about 370 mm, and the distance between the filter set and the detector was about 40 mm.

190 **3 Results and discussion**

191 **3.1 Validation of MC simulations**

192 A comparison of the ISO 4037-3:2019 CCs with the simulated CC values for the source in 0.32 g/cm^2
193 steel encapsulation is summarized in Table 2. The relative differences, RD, are between -0.4% and
194 -1.7%. Better agreement is obtained when the CCs are calculated with added filter 0.25 mm Cu
195 + 0.4 mm Al effectively removing all photons below 25 keV only or using updated monoenergetic
196 CCs [5]. As the details of the conditions used to determine the ISO 4037-estimated CCs are not
197 known, more specific conclusions cannot be drawn. However, the RDs are well below the expected
198 uncertainty of the CCs in ISO 4037.

199 **3.2 Simulated CCs with additional filtration**

200 The dependence of $h_K^*(10; \text{S-Am})$ on area density of added filtration for selected combinations
201 of the source construction and the filter material obtained from MC simulations is presented in
202 Figure 4 for distances of 50 cm and 200 cm. Data obtained for Al filtration only are not shown in
203 the plots because the results were outside of the y-scale. It is observed that the CC value changes
204 significantly with the added filtration for low total area density of source encapsulation. For some
205 combinations of additional filtration, a saturation of CC value is reached suggesting that an optimal
206 filter combination can be found.

Table 2. Comparison of conversion coefficients from ISO 4037 and those calculated in this study at 200 cm from the source encapsulated in 0.32 g/cm² steel. ⁽¹⁾ ISO 4037-3:2019 monoenergetic CCs. ⁽²⁾ ISO 4037-3:2019 monoenergetic CCs, MC simulations with added filter 0.25 mm Cu + 0.4 mm Al. ⁽³⁾ monoenergetic CCs from [5], MC simulations with added filter 0.25 mm Cu + 0.4 mm Al.

	ISO 4037-3:2019	This study ⁽¹⁾	This study ⁽²⁾	This study ⁽³⁾
$h'_K(0, 07; S-Am, 0^\circ)$	1.59	-0.89%	-0.55%	-0.30%
$h_K^*(10; S-Am)$	1.74	-1.27%	-0.64%	-0.05%
$h_{pK}(0, 07; S-Am)_{pill}$	1.39	-0.65%	-0.35%	0.02%
$h_{pK}(0, 07; S-Am)_{rod}$	1.14	-0.38%	-0.24%	0.16%
$h_{pK}(0, 07; S-Am, 0^\circ)_{slab}$	1.72	-1.67%	-1.34%	-0.80%
$h_{pK}(10; S-Am, 0^\circ)_{slab}$	1.89	-1.61%	-0.95%	-0.38%

207 It is shown in Figure 5 that with a filter combination of 0.25 mm of Cu followed by 0.4 mm
 208 of Al, not only $h_K^*(10; S-Am)$, but all the CCs are within 0.5% of fully saturated values. (The
 209 exception to this is $h'_K(0.07; S-Am, 180^\circ)$ and $h'_K(3; S-Am, 180^\circ)$, with which the absolute value is
 210 below 0.1 Sv/Gy).

211 For selected filter combinations, the MC calculated fluence spectra at a distance of 200 cm
 212 from the source are depicted in Figure 6.

213 The results of the Monte Carlo simulations can be concluded as follows:

- 214 • Studied steel and Cu filtration (or encapsulation) generate characteristic X-rays to an extent that
 215 influences the CCs significantly (Air, Cu; CER+0.05ss, ss and CER+0.05ss, Cu in Figure 4).
 216 This is also the case for a recommended steel encapsulation from ISO 4037-3:2019.
- 217 • An Al filter added behind the main Cu or steel filter effectively removes the characteristic
 218 photons emitted from the main filter. Characteristic X-rays generated in Al have an energy
 219 less than 1.6 keV and are fully absorbed in a thin layer of air behind the filter.
- 220 • The results indicate that a sandwich of a 0.25 mm (0.224 g/cm²) thick Cu filter followed by
 221 a 0.4 mm thick Al filter removes the majority of low energy photons from the fluence spec-
 222 trum, and makes the CC values independent (within 0.3% for $h_K^*(10; S-Am)$) of the source
 223 encapsulation and of further increases in Cu filter thickness. Verification by measurements
 224 is described in the next section.
- 225 • Drawbacks of filtration made of steel include the variability of elemental composition and
 226 density, and the production of characteristic photons from elements with high atomic number
 227 (e.g. molybdenum) present in some types of steel. Therefore, 0.4 mm of Al might not be
 228 sufficient to attenuate all characteristic photons generated by the steel filter (or encapsulation).
 229 Knowledge of steel composition would be required to use it for the proposed purpose. For
 230 these reasons, Cu was deemed a more suitable primary filter material.

231 3.3 Measured spectra with added filtration

232 Measured detector spectra for the first filter made of Cu with a thickness of 0.105 mm, 0.21 mm,
 233 0.26 mm, and 0.317 mm are presented in Figure 7. 16-22 keV photons from Am-241 were detected

Figure 4. Monte Carlo simulations of the relative difference, RD, between $h_K^*(10; \text{S-Am})$ value presented in Table 3, $h_K^*(10)_{\text{ref}}$, and the value for another selected source and filter combinations, $h_K^*(10)_x$, at a distance of 50 cm (upper) and 200 cm (lower) from the source. $\text{RD} = \frac{h_K^*(10)_x}{h_K^*(10)_{\text{ref}}} - 1$. Legend: Source description first, followed by filter description. Air = point source, no encapsulation. CER+ss = source in ceramics encapsulated in the given area density (in g/cm^2) of stainless steel (ss). Cu, Cu+Al, ss, ss+Al stands for the composition of the main filter and the second filter (0.4 mm of Al, if any).

234 and distinguished from the spectrum continuum up to a thickness of the Cu filter of 0.21 mm, while
 235 for 0.26 mm and larger thicknesses their possible contribution was below the detection threshold.
 236 With a 0.26 mm thick copper filter, the measured fluence of 26 keV photons was decreased by a factor
 237 of 54 (theoretical decrease by a factor of 39). The discrepancy between the measured and theoretical
 238 decrease may stem from the use of simple methods to determine the theoretical attenuation and the
 239 peak areas from the measured spectra. However, the precise value of the attenuation is not crucial
 240 as long as the fluence behind the filters is sufficiently reduced, as shown in the measured spectra.

241 Measured detector spectra for the second filter made of aluminum with a thickness of 0.3 mm,

Figure 5. Results from the Monte Carlo simulations showing the relative difference in the CC values, where one CC value was determined with a recommended filtration thickness (0.25 mm of Cu and 0.4 mm of Al, X_{rec}), and the other with a filtration thickness required for full CC saturation (0.6 g/cm² (0.67 mm) of Cu and 0.4 mm of Al, X_{sat}). y-axis shows the value of $X_{rec}/X_{sat}-1$. The results are presented for two distances from the source. The fully saturated CC values (in Sv/Gy) from Table 3 calculated with monoenergetic CCs from [5] are provided in the figure.

Figure 6. Monte Carlo simulated fluence spectra at 200 cm from the source with different additional filtration and source encapsulation. ⁽¹⁾Point source, no encapsulation. ⁽²⁾Volume source in ceramics, 0.32 g/cm² steel encapsulation. The spectra were normalized to the fluence in the energy bin of 59.5 keV photons.

242 0.4 mm, and 0.5 mm are presented in Figure 8. 8.0 keV and 8.9 keV peaks of characteristic photons
 243 from a Cu filter are detectable with the applied Al filter thickness up to 0.3 mm. For such thickness,
 244 the area of 8.0 keV and 8.9 keV peaks decreased by a factor of 53 corresponding to the theoretical

Figure 7. Close view on detector spectra of EG type Am-241 source measured with applied various thicknesses of a Cu filter. Outside of the view the spectra were practically identical. Spectra were normalized to the same area of 59.5 keV peak. The peaks around 28 keV are Cd and Te escape peaks of 59.5 keV photons i.e., they are caused by detector effects and are not part of the radiation beam.

Figure 8. Close view on detector spectra of ANG300 Am-241 source measured with 0.26 mm Cu filter followed by various thicknesses of an Al filter. Outside of the view the spectra were practically identical. Spectra were normalized to the same area of the 59.5 keV peak. Peaks at 7.5 keV and 8.3 keV in all spectra are characteristic peaks of nickel present in the detector cover, i.e., they are caused by detector effects and are not part of the radiation beam.

245 decrease of 8.0 keV peak by a factor of 59. The measurements showed that the Al filter of a thickness
 246 of 0.4 mm placed behind the Cu filter is sufficient for the removal of characteristic photons from the
 247 Cu filter (theoretical decrease by a factor of 230) at a distance of 45 cm used in the measurement.
 248 At distances of 100 cm and 200 cm, the fluence of 8 keV photons would decrease by additional 48%
 249 and 84%, respectively.

250 The results measured at ENEA are visualized in Figure 9. The recommended filtration reduced
 251 the area of the 26 keV peak by a factor of 42, although the factor is highly uncertain due to
 252 small area of the peak in the filtered spectrum. The spectrum for the non-filtered beam contained

Figure 9. Measured detector spectra at ENEA without (green) and with (blue) the recommended filtration, zoomed at different parts of the spectrum. The attenuation of photons from all emissions below 27 keV from decay of Am-241 can be seen from the spectra. The left side figure also illustrates in the non filtered spectrum the presence of characteristic X-rays from lead source collimator at 10.5 keV and 12.6 keV, and from iron at 6.4 keV. The peaks around 28 keV are Cd and Te escape peaks and peaks between 7.5 keV and 8.5 keV are most likely characteristic peaks of Cu and Zn present in the brass separator that is provided from the manufacturer as part of the collimation kit, and of Ni from the detector cover. There was no copper present in the beam with the non-filtered beam, and the peak area does not change with the added filtration. Therefore the peaks are not part of the beam, and are caused by detector effects. See Figures 7 and 8 for comparison.

253 possibly characteristic peaks from copper due to a presence of brass in the detector collimation
 254 set-up. However, the area of these peaks remained unchanged in the filtered spectrum, and the
 255 attenuation of characteristic X-rays from iron was demonstrated by the results. Therefore, the
 256 ENEA measurements confirmed the results of CMI.

257 3.4 High energy photons from neutron reactions

258 The alpha particles from decay of Am-241 can lead to neutron production through (α, n) reactions
 259 with oxygen or aluminum in the source matrix or surrounding materials. From [16], the neutron
 260 yield of an Am-241 source was $1.8 \cdot 10^{-7}$ per decay. In addition to neutrons, gamma rays are
 261 produced in these events through relaxation of the atom after the (α, n) reaction and through
 262 neutron inelastic scattering. As an overestimation, one 2.5 MeV photon per (α, n) reaction would
 263 reach the measurement point with the same probability as the 59.5 keV photons. Using equation
 264 (2.1), $(\mu_{tr}/\rho)_E$ from PENELLOPE [17] and CCs from ISO 4037-3:2019, the contribution to $h_K^*(10)$
 265 from the 2.5 MeV photons would be less than 0.001% of that of the 59.5 keV photons. Although
 266 the neutron production might depend on the source construction, the neutron yield could be two
 267 orders of magnitude higher, and still the contribution to photon CCs would be negligible. Using the
 268 neutron yield of 1.8×10^{-7} and conversion coefficients from neutron fluence to ambient dose from
 269 ISO 8529-3 [18] at 5 MeV energy (the maximum energy of the neutrons from [16]), the contribution
 270 of neutrons to the ambient dose is less than 0.1% of the gamma dose.

271 3.5 Recommendation for filtered S-Am beams

272 Based on the results of Monte Carlo simulations and measurements, to achieve a beam for which
 273 generic CCs can be used without the knowledge of the source encapsulation and without the need

274 for spectrometry, the recommended filtration for the S-Am beams is 0.25 mm of Cu followed by
275 0.4 mm of Al. For a collimated beam, filtration should be added to the external aperture of the source
276 collimator to also remove characteristic photons from the collimator's material. For an uncollimated
277 beam, the filtration should be positioned as close as possible to the source (although it should be
278 noted that ISO 4037 does not allow use of uncollimated sources at the moment). The filtration results
279 in Am-241 fluence spectra, which, from CC determination point of view, are practically independent
280 of the source encapsulation because low energy photons passing through source encapsulation, or
281 characteristic X-rays generated in the source encapsulation were removed from the fluence spectra.
282 If the encapsulation is thicker than 0.32 g/cm², which is the recommended minimal value in [1],
283 the potentially increased number of scattered photons in the thicker encapsulation or filtration does
284 not change the CC value significantly (Figure 4). Consequently, a single value for the CCs can be
285 recommended and considered as a reference for any S-Am field where the recommended filtration
286 is applied. The generic CCs are given in Table 3.

287 The uncertainty of the generic CC values was estimated to be 0.2% ($k = 1$). It consists of the
288 uncertainty in the calculated spectral distribution of photon fluence owing to cross-section table
289 uncertainty. However, this estimate does not include the uncertainty of the published monoenergetic
290 CC values.

291 As the measured fluence spectra may contain artifacts because of measurements statistics,
292 as well as an imprecise response matrix influencing the unfolding process, the recommended CC
293 values were rather calculated from MC simulated photon fluence spectra, which were considered
294 to be more accurate. The CC values were derived at a distance of 50 cm from the volume source
295 (see the construction in section 2.2) for a filter with a surface density of 0.6 g/cm² (0.67 mm) of Cu
296 followed by a 0.4 mm thick Al filter. CC values valid for the recommended filter thickness do not
297 differ from the values in Table 3 more than presented in Figure 5, i.e., typically by 0.2% but not
298 more than by 0.5% (except for $h'_K(0.07; \text{S-Am}, 180^\circ)$ and $h'_K(3; \text{S-Am}, 180^\circ)$). Relative differences
299 are much lower for an Am-241 source with the 0.32 g/cm² steel encapsulation, because the MC
300 simulations were performed for a thinner encapsulation (0.05 g/cm²).

301 Adding the filtration to the S-Am beam has additional benefits. The purpose of using Am-241
302 sources for dosimeter calibrations is to have a calibration point at the approximately 60 keV energy
303 of the main peak of Am-241. With some detectors, for example open air ionization chambers, the
304 detection efficiency for low energy photons can be high, whereas with other detectors these photons
305 are detected with a small probability. For example a PTW 32002 chamber (spherical chamber one
306 liter) has approximately 3 mm thick wall made mostly of polyoxymethylene. Using mass attenuation
307 coefficients from NIST XCOM [19], and a density of 1.415 g/cm³, less than 5% of photons with
308 8 keV energy reach the cavity volume of the chamber.

309 In a non-filtered S-Am beam, if a detector with a low detection efficiency at low energies is
310 calibrated for air kerma, the detector does not detect the low energy photons present in the beam,
311 although they are included in the reference air kerma value. If the instrument being calibrated
312 would be used in the same beam with the given calibration coefficient, it would give correct results
313 for the air kerma. However, in another beam, if the contribution of the low energy photons differs
314 from the source used for the calibration of that detector (which would be caused, for example, by a
315 difference in the source window thickness as shown in Figure 4), the air kerma would be measured
316 incorrectly. Also, even though the CCs would be calculated from spectrometric measurements,

317 applying the CCs would give incorrect results due to the incorrect air kerma measurement. The
318 energy response of a third instrument being calibrated would complicate the situation even further.
319 Using the recommended additional filtration in both beams would reduce these issues, and the
320 spectra between laboratories would be more similar. Also, the spectra would resemble more a
321 monoenergetic 59.5 keV beam (columns $\Delta 59.5$ keV in Table 3), and therefore make the beam more
322 suitable for energy response determination, which is the basic intention of the use of such beam.

323 The thickness and material composition of the recommended added filtration causes the de-
324 crease of air kerma rate by 30% compared to the air kerma rate without the filtration, for an Am-241
325 source encapsulated with 0.32 g/cm^2 of stainless steel. This is a necessary trade-off for the use of
326 the proposed method instead of performing a spectrometric characterization of the S-Am beam or
327 performing a calibration for each CC. The air kerma rate would decrease even more for an Am-
328 241 source with thinner encapsulation, because more low energy photons pass through the source
329 encapsulation.

330 4 Conclusions

331 An optimal filtration thickness, that would allow use of generic CCs without spectrometry for S-Am
332 beams intended for radiation protection meter calibrations, regardless of the source encapsulation
333 thickness, was determined to be 0.25 mm of copper followed by 0.4 mm of aluminum. The
334 recommended generic CCs, that can be used with the applied filtration, are given in Table 3. The
335 filters should be placed on top of the collimator aperture to attenuate characteristic X-rays from
336 the collimation as well. It was found that the source capsule made of stainless steel affects the CC
337 values significantly due to the production of characteristic X-rays in the capsule, regardless of the
338 capsule thickness.

339 The low energy photon contribution to the air kerma without the added filtration differs between
340 different source encapsulations, and therefore spectra between various calibration beams without
341 added filtration might differ significantly. Using the recommended filtration would make all S-Am
342 beams more similar, and would remove issues related to detector response at low energies. Also, the
343 calibration beams would resemble more a monoenergetic 59.5 keV beam. Therefore, the authors
344 recommend using the filters with all S-Am beams, regardless of whether the spectrometry method
345 could be used or not. However, this recommendation would need to be applied throughout all levels
346 of the calibration chain, starting from the primary laboratory and ending at the calibrations for end
347 users of survey meters.

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Table 3. Recommended CC values for S-Am beams, where the filtration of at least 0.25 mm of Cu and 0.4 mm of Al is applied. The values have been calculated for a Monte-Carlo simulated spectrum at 50 cm distance from the source with 0.6 g/cm² (0.67 mm) of Cu and 0.4 mm of Al filtration. ¹Values calculated with monoenergetic CCs from ISO 4037-3:2019 [2]. ²Values calculated with recalculated monoenergetic CCs from [5]. $\Delta 59.5$ keV is the difference to the value of a monoenergetic CC at the main gamma peak energy of Am-241 at 59.5 keV.

	CC value ¹ (Sv/Gy)	$\Delta 59.5$ keV ¹ (%)	CC value ² (Sv/Gy)	$\Delta 59.5$ keV ² (%)
$h'_K(0, 07; \text{S-Am}, 0^\circ)$	1.5847	-0.22	1.5890	-0.24
$h'_K(0, 07; \text{S-Am}, 15^\circ)$	1.5644	-0.22	1.5843	-0.24
$h'_K(0, 07; \text{S-Am}, 30^\circ)$	1.5544	-0.22	1.5704	-0.24
$h'_K(0, 07; \text{S-Am}, 45^\circ)$	1.5544	-0.22	1.5457	-0.25
$h'_K(0, 07; \text{S-Am}, 60^\circ)$	1.5436	-0.26	1.5058	-0.25
$h'_K(0, 07; \text{S-Am}, 75^\circ)$	1.4643	-0.24	1.4408	-0.26
$h'_K(0, 07; \text{S-Am}, 90^\circ)$	1.1146	-0.30	1.2475	-0.35
$h'_K(0, 07; \text{S-Am}, 180^\circ)$	0.0401	-1.10	0.0350	-1.97
$h'_K(3; \text{S-Am}, 0^\circ)$	1.6734	-0.27	1.6741	-0.29
$h'_K(3; \text{S-Am}, 15^\circ)$	1.6725	-0.30	1.6682	-0.30
$h'_K(3; \text{S-Am}, 30^\circ)$	1.6525	-0.30	1.6478	-0.30
$h'_K(3; \text{S-Am}, 45^\circ)$	1.6125	-0.31	1.6074	-0.30
$h'_K(3; \text{S-Am}, 60^\circ)$	1.5325	-0.32	1.5315	-0.32
$h'_K(3; \text{S-Am}, 75^\circ)$	1.3725	-0.34	1.3737	-0.36
$h'_K(3; \text{S-Am}, 90^\circ)$	0.9623	-0.52	0.9623	-0.52
$h'_K(3; \text{S-Am}, 180^\circ)$	0.0401	-1.90	0.0409	-1.96
$h_K^*(10; \text{S-Am})$	1.7340	-0.27	1.7414	-0.36
$h_{pK}(0, 07; \text{S-Am})_{\text{rod}}$	1.1380	-0.09	1.1414	-0.10
$h_{pK}(0, 07; \text{S-Am})_{\text{pill}}$	1.3858	-0.14	1.3903	-0.13
$h_{pK}(0, 07; \text{S-Am}, 0^\circ)_{\text{slab}}$	1.7028	-0.28	1.7088	-0.30
$h_{pK}(0, 07; \text{S-Am}, 15^\circ)_{\text{slab}}$	1.6733	-0.26	1.7012	-0.29
$h_{pK}(0, 07; \text{S-Am}, 30^\circ)_{\text{slab}}$	1.6323	-0.29	1.6790	-0.30
$h_{pK}(0, 07; \text{S-Am}, 45^\circ)_{\text{slab}}$	1.5534	-0.27	1.6356	-0.28
$h_{pK}(0, 07; \text{S-Am}, 60^\circ)_{\text{slab}}$	1.4231	-0.28	1.5580	-0.28
$h_{pK}(0, 07; \text{S-Am}, 75^\circ)_{\text{slab}}$	1.3129	-0.27	1.4211	-0.28
$h_{pK}(3; \text{S-Am}, 0^\circ)_{\text{cyl}}$	1.6637	-0.27	1.6593	-0.27
$h_{pK}(3; \text{S-Am}, 15^\circ)_{\text{cyl}}$	1.6535	-0.28	1.6555	-0.28
$h_{pK}(3; \text{S-Am}, 30^\circ)_{\text{cyl}}$	1.6335	-0.28	1.6371	-0.28
$h_{pK}(3; \text{S-Am}, 45^\circ)_{\text{cyl}}$	1.6036	-0.28	1.6023	-0.28
$h_{pK}(3; \text{S-Am}, 60^\circ)_{\text{cyl}}$	1.5333	-0.29	1.5380	-0.30
$h_{pK}(3; \text{S-Am}, 75^\circ)_{\text{cyl}}$	1.4026	-0.33	1.4103	-0.35
$h_{pK}(3; \text{S-Am}, 90^\circ)_{\text{cyl}}$	1.1012	-0.48	1.1014	-0.46
$h_{pK}(10; \text{S-Am}, 0^\circ)_{\text{slab}}$	1.8797	-0.38	1.8883	-0.41
$h_{pK}(10; \text{S-Am}, 15^\circ)_{\text{slab}}$	1.8589	-0.41	1.8709	-0.42
$h_{pK}(10; \text{S-Am}, 30^\circ)_{\text{slab}}$	1.8186	-0.41	1.8144	-0.42
$h_{pK}(10; \text{S-Am}, 45^\circ)_{\text{slab}}$	1.7063	-0.49	1.7030	-0.42
$h_{pK}(10; \text{S-Am}, 60^\circ)_{\text{slab}}$	1.4897	-0.44	1.4862	-0.46
$h_{pK}(10; \text{S-Am}, 75^\circ)_{\text{slab}}$	1.0482	-0.64	1.0313	-0.59

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